

STUDIES ON HYDRATION AND SWELLING OF THE ORGANIC COMPLEXES OF MONTMORILLONITE

BY H. MUKERJEE

The hydrophilic character of montmorillonite, as measured by hydration studies, has been generally found to be reduced by the introduction of organic groups in it and the resulting montmorillonite complexes become, to a certain extent, organophilic. Krilium, water-soluble polyacrylonitrile, and itself, hydrophilic, is adsorbed to a considerable extent by bentonite, rendering the product more hydrophilic than the original clay.

The water of hydration by clays is believed to be non-liquid in character and appears largely on the basal plane surfaces of the expanding lattice minerals of montmorillonite. This non-liquid water possesses a strong orientation by virtue of the dipolar character and the electrical charge on the clay-mineral surface. Consequently, as Hendricks and Jefferson (*Proc. Soil Sci. Amer. Soc.*, 1940, 5, 95) postulate, the water molecules may form a hexagonal network through extensive hydrogen bonding between water and clay mineral surface.

Grim ("Clay Mineralogy", McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., New York, 1953) and Hendricks (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1457) investigated the influence of the saturating cation on the nature and amount of adsorbed water.

Gieseking (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, 47, 1) has found that the water-sorption capacity of clay is reduced often to zero, when they are saturated with amines, which are adsorbed on the basal plane surfaces of montmorillonite.

The object of the present investigation is to show the change in the hydrophilic nature of bentonite by the introduction of organic radicals to the clay surface by means of swelling and hydration studies.

Since it is necessary in the assessment of the amount of adsorbed water, the contribution of capillary water, the amount of water in the pores of montmorillonites, has been measured, as usual, by using a non-polar liquid and determining the intake of the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

The organic complexes were prepared by treating the electrodiállysed clay with one and a half times the weight of the organic substances, viz., gelatin, albumin, brucine, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), aniline, diethylamine, krilium and humus and allowing the mixture to shake for six hours in an end-to-end shaker. After keeping overnight, the unadsorbed portion of the organic reactant was removed by washing in the centrifuge. The treated clay, thus obtained, was dried under an infra-red lamp, powdered and sieved through 100 mesh and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator

Measurement of Hydration.—Hydration was studied by measuring the adsorption of water vapour by the treated clays when they were kept in close chambers

maintained at different vapour pressures (Puri *et al.*, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1925, 15, 68; Thomas, *Soil Sci.*, 1924, 17, 1). The constant vapour pressure chambers were made of large petri-dishes, thoroughly sealed on glass plate with vaseline. Small petri-dishes containing definite proportions of H_2SO_4 (conc.) and water (International Critical Table, Vol. III, p. 303, McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., New York, 1928) were kept inside these chambers in order to maintain the desired vapour pressures. Weighed quantities of the samples were spread in very small and shallow petri-dishes and were kept inside the constant vapour pressure chambers in order to attain equilibrium. After 72 hours the increase in weight was determined from which the amount of water vapour per 100 g. of clay was calculated. Preliminary experiments showed that after 72 hours negligibly small amounts of water vapour were taken up.

Measurement of Swelling.—The swelling of treated and untreated clays was measured according to a method recommended by Baver ("Soil Physics", John Willy and Sons, Inc., New York, 1946) using toluene as the non-polar liquid. The final value of the intake was recorded after 4 hours in each case. The very small and continuous intake even after 4 hours was neglected. This is perhaps admissible for a comparative study. The results are represented in Figs. 1 and 2 and also in Table I.

TABLE I

Results of swelling studies.
Intake of liquid per g. of sample.

Sample.	Water.	Toluene.	Sample.	Water.	Toluene
H-clay	2.44 c.c.	0.99 c. c.	Clay-aniline (1 : 0.25)	1.72 c. c.	1.01 c.c.
H-clay-gelatin	1.90	0.85	Clay-aniline (1 : 1.5)	1.41	0.96
H-clay-albumin	1.06	0.71	Clay-CTAB	1.22	5.94
Clay-humus	2.42	0.97	Clay-diethylamine	1.37	1.01
Clay-brucine	1.67	1.05	Clay-krillium (20%)	4.60	0.875

DISCUSSION

Figs. 1 and 2 show very clearly that at any particular vapour pressure the organic clay complexes adsorb smaller amounts of water than the untreated clay. Each organic clay complex, however, shows a gradual increase of adsorption as the vapour pressure is increased. Some of them even show an unmistakable inflexion, e.g., albumin, gelatin and brucine. The hydration capacity, *i.e.* the amount of water vapour adsorbed per 100 g. of the system, is lowest in case of brucine, CTAB diethylamine, followed by gelatin, albumin, aniline, humus, H-clay and krillium in increasing order. Gelatin, albumin and humus, although they themselves are hydrophilic, apparently render the clay less hydrophilic, possibly by mutually saturating the sites responsible for hydration. On the other hand, krillium-treated clays have higher hydration capacities than H-clay, particularly at higher proportion of krillium. Krillium, it may be mentioned, readily adsorbs water and possibly as a

result of combination with the H-clay, the capacity for hydration also decreases, as it is so with humus, but the decrease perhaps is too small.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The results of swelling measurements support the observations of the hydration studies discussed above. The small water-intake and very high toluene-intake of C.T.A.B.-treated clay show that the cetyl derivative has become organophilic in character. Except the krillium-clay complex, the others possess a lower intake than the original H-clay. The water intake of gelatin-treated clay is greater than that of albumin-treated clay which reflects the greater swelling capacity of gelatin, compared to albumin. The proteins are highly adsorbed by the clays, but do not impart thereby any marked organophilic character to the proteinated clays. In these and similar cases of brucine and amine; the hydrophilic character is reduced but the

products do not become noticeably organophilic except in the case of C.T.A.B-treated clay which becomes highly organophilic. Clay having adsorbed ksilium, on the other hand, becomes highly hydrophilic as a result of the dominating influence of ksilium itself.

The author's thanks are due to Dr. S. K., Mukherjee, D.Sc., Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, for his guidance and providing laboratory facilities.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA

Received November 19, 1955.